

Quantitative Insights into Financial Resilience for Sustainable Business: A DuPont and Fundamental Performance Assessment of Hero MotoCorp and TVS Motor Company

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Abstract

While the Indian automobile manufacturers mark their global presence, it is important for them to maintain their financial health. This study aims to evaluate the same using metrics such as Ratio analysis, DuPont Analysis, and other measures to analyse the key trends of two companies Hero MotoCorp and TVS Motor Company.

Keywords: Financial Resilience, Quantitative Insights, Sustainable Business, DuPont Analysis, Ratio analysis

JEL Classification: G0, G2, G3, F0, F2, F6

Introduction

Indian automobile sector has seen many drastic changes in the last decade. With a global shift towards sustainable mobility, and the rising demand for performance vehicles, the Indian manufacturers have adapted themselves and positioned themselves to join the global trend. While they have joined the global trend by having joint ventures, mergers and acquisitions and technological collaborations to achieve this, it has a direct bearing on the finances of the company. The company needs to restructure its finances to achieve this objective.

Such stress on the companies, especially amid the COVID-19 crisis, does not prove to be good, especially if the companies are not able to cater to their existing shareholders. While joining the global trend may be for the best for the company and the ecosystem, the financial stress should not have a bearing on the sector or economy in the case of an adversary, and hence the need for the study.

Review of literature

Mr. Shino P. Jose and Prof. Dr. T. Ashokan conducted a focused study on Ashok Leyland Ltd., identifying two major categories of corporate actions during the review period—namely, Financial Results (coded as 2) and Production/Project/New Initiatives (coded as 5). To determine the impact of these initiatives on share price movements, the researchers collected and analysed data from January 2014 to December 2016. They mapped financial outcomes and

operational milestones to stock price trends, using a pre- and post-announcement comparison method to evaluate the influence of these events on investor behaviour and market response.

Chauhan (2014) performed a fundamental analysis to evaluate the performance of India's automobile sector. The study centered on comparing financial metrics of key players—Tata Motors Ltd. and Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.—using key financial ratios to assess their overall efficiency. Joshi (2017) conducted a fundamental evaluation of selected automobile companies using critical performance indicators to guide effective portfolio construction.

Dhole (2013) examined the relationship between corporate performance and stock price movements. Her research aimed to identify various internal and external factors that significantly influence share prices, suggesting that robust company performance has a direct bearing on investor confidence and market valuation.

Kumar (2013) applied the Economy-Industry-Company (EIC) analysis to compare several firms within the automobile sector. The study relied on financial ratios such as Return on Equity (ROE), Price to Earnings (P/E), and Dividend per Share (DPS), and computed intrinsic values to determine fair value estimates. It was concluded that such valuation techniques are essential for sound portfolio decisions.

Khanifar (2012) extended the analysis to behavioural aspects by identifying factors influencing investment decisions within Tehran's stock market. His study integrated macroeconomic, industry-specific, and firm-level analysis, revealing that metrics such as Earnings per Share (EPS), profit margins, and P/E ratios are given the highest weight by analysts, followed by economic and industry trends.

Kulkarni (2013) explored the comparative strengths of technical and fundamental analysis, identifying sectors that are more receptive to either approach. The findings suggested that certain industries exhibit better predictability under technical frameworks, while others align more with fundamental analysis. In line with this, Sadhwani (2019) conducted a technical analysis of stocks listed under NIFTY AUTO, optimizing selection parameters to enhance forecasting accuracy.

Hansda and Ray investigated inter-market relationships, focusing on technology stocks traded on the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) and Indian exchanges like BSE and NSE. The researchers found that while causality existed in stock movement between NYSE and domestic technology counters, the overall domestic indices and technology stock prices remained uncorrelated.

Patil, Gupta, and Singh documented the transformation of the National Stock Exchange (NSE) into a highly computerized, investor-centric trading platform. Their study emphasized NSE's role in embracing global best practices, ensuring bias-free operations, and building a resilient trading infrastructure that supports transparency and innovation in the Indian capital markets.

Lazar, Priya, and Jeyapaul (2005) analysed monthly return data from the BSE Sensitivity Index (Sensex) over a 14-year period, revealing clear seasonal patterns in returns. Their findings provided evidence of inefficiencies in the Indian stock market, thereby highlighting potential opportunities for timing-based investment strategies.

Das and Patnayak (2009) explored financial indicators that influence share prices and overall market performance. Their research found a positive correlation between strong earnings

potential, favourable ROI, and growth prospects with share price appreciation. Conversely, elevated risk and volatility were linked with declining investor interest and price depreciation. These variables were positioned as critical tools for investors, corporations, and analysts in decision-making processes.

Agarwal (2011) examined how demographic factors such as gender, occupation, age, and marital status influence investment behaviour. The study found that these variables affected the source and credibility of investment advice, which in turn shaped herd behaviour and future investment choices. Furthermore, the research offered insights into household saving preferences and their relationship with asset pricing anomalies.

Nirmala and Gomathi (2012) conducted a technical study on select construction firms listed on the NIFTY 50 index. Utilizing indicators such as the exponential moving average, Rate of Change (ROC), and Relative Strength Index (RSI), the researchers tracked share performance over 145 days. Their analysis highlighted meaningful correlations between stock price behaviour and broader market trends, recommending targeted holding periods to maximize investor returns.

E. Geetha and Swaminathan (2015) conducted a study to identify the key factors influencing stock market prices. Focusing on four companies from the automobile and IT sectors listed on BSE and NSE, they used four metrics—Earnings Per Share (EPS), Book Value, Price-to-Earnings (P/E) Ratio, and Dividend Yield. Their analysis showed that while EPS, Book Value, and the P/E Ratio significantly influenced stock prices, Dividend Yield had no noticeable effect.

John William and T. Vimla (2015) evaluated volatility in selected banking stocks through beta analysis, using data from audited annual reports for the years 2013–2014. Their study spanned the pre- and post-crisis periods and concluded that fluctuations in market conditions influenced equity share prices. ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, Axis Bank, PNB, and IndusInd Bank showed elevated risk, as indicated by higher beta values. This approach provided a framework for identifying viable equity investments.

Dr. P. Karthikeyan and S. Dinesh Kumar (2016) analysed the performance of construction firms listed on NSE using simple moving averages and trend analysis for the period from January 2014 to July 2016. Their findings suggested that companies such as DLF Ltd., Oberoi Realty Ltd., NCC Ltd., and Prestige Estates Ltd. displayed positive investment signals. Conversely, Ashok Buildcon Ltd. was seen as a sell due to its prices falling below the average, with DLF Ltd. emerging as the most favourable investment.

Robert P. Schumaker and Nick Maida (2018) explored the relationship between financial news, media influence, and stock price changes. Using the Sharpe Ratio to assess risk-adjusted returns over 40 trading days (Feb 12–Apr 10, 2014), their study revealed a strong link between news sentiment and stock price movements. They confirmed that financial news significantly shapes investor behaviour and market pricing.

Pravin Choudhary and Prof. Apoorva Bhatnagar (2018) carried out a technical analysis of share price movements in selected PSUs from Jan to Dec 2017. Their findings indicated that market indices heavily influenced prices of companies like Coal India Ltd., ONGC, GAIL, Indian Oil Corporation, and Power Grid Corporation.

Smriti Menon (2018) undertook a comparative study between BSE and global markets using secondary data and statistical tools in MS Excel. The findings rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate, confirming differences in behaviour between BSE and NYSE.

Sukhmander Singh and Deepak Kumar (2018) aimed to identify global market trends from 2014–2018. Using descriptive and correlation analyses, the authors investigated cross-country market relationships and highlighted how international linkages shape national market behaviour.

Dr. Mayur Savsani and Uravi Rathod (2018) compared stock market and banking sector risk-return profiles using weekly BSE data from 2005–2017. Employing standard deviation and t-tests, analysed through IBM SPSS and Excel, they assessed volatility to guide investor decisions.

Sameer Yadav (2017) examined multiple factors contributing to market volatility using data from SEBI, RBI, BSE, and NSE. The study concluded that inflation rates, interest rates, budget announcements, and credit policy changes were major drivers. Mitigation strategies like circuit breakers and pre-trading sessions were discussed.

Pankaj Srivastava and Mr. Ugrasen (2017) explored stock market conditions with respect to financial trends. Using secondary sources, they emphasized that increasing public participation requires improved financial literacy and trust-building measures from the government.

Mrunal Chetan Bhai Joshi and Yashika Batra (2017) focused on investor perception. Using surveys and structured questionnaires, they found that 90% of investors regularly invested in the market, while 10% were speculative participants. Key influencing factors included P/E ratio and EPS.

Namitha K. Cheriyan and Daniel Lazar (2017) used intraday data for 50 securities over the period January–December 2016 to analyse trading activity and liquidity. Their study applied least square regression and identified high liquidity-driven volatility in the stock market.

Sadhan Kumar Chattopadhyay and Samir Ranjan Behera (2017) examined the BSE index using daily data of 30 scrips. They conducted Granger Causality and Co-integration tests to assess the interdependence of Indian markets with developed markets like the USA, UK, and Hong Kong. The results indicated positive return spillovers and growing global integration.

Edwin Prabu A., Indrani Bhattacharya, and Partha Roy (2016) explored the linkage between Indian stock markets and monetary policy. Using treasury bill rates and robustness checks, they found that policy changes directly influence stock market behaviour and, in turn, the broader economy.

Aditya Bharadwaj, Yogendra Narayan, Vanraj, Pawan, and Maitreyee Dutta (2015) applied sentiment analysis using Python to determine how investor opinions, emotions, and textual data influenced investment decisions. Their study emphasized the roles of Sensex and Nifty in tracking future market trends.

Madhvi (2014) conducted an extensive study using secondary data from RBI bulletins and websites of BSE and NSE to understand market behaviour post-globalization up to 2005. Findings suggested that recession periods led to fluctuating returns, and incomplete information often resulted in negative returns.

Ms. Anju Bala (2013) analysed how macroeconomic variables like inflation, money supply, GDP, and fiscal deficit affect the Indian stock market. She concluded that these factors significantly impact market movements and investor sentiments.

Mahamuni P. N. and Poma A. A. (2019) used the DuPont model to analyse profitability in Bajaj Auto. They found that Bajaj Auto's cost-efficiency led to higher margins and stronger financial performance.

Kumar R. (2018) focused on Bajaj Auto's profitability and highlighted the firm's strategy to target high-margin international markets. They concluded that this approach allowed the company to maintain a stable and profitable financial position.

Sneha (2017) studied Bajaj Auto's financial health by evaluating its debt-to-equity ratio and interest coverage ratio. These indicators provided insights into the firm's debt management and capacity to meet financial obligations.

Objective of the study

- Evaluation of the financial performance of TVS Motor Company and Hero MotoCorp.
- Study the components that contribute to the ROE through DuPont Analysis.
- Study the liquidity of the companies using ratio analysis.

Scope

- Study of liquidity and turnover using ratio analysis.
- Decomposition of ROE and a study of its key constituents.

Methodology

- The research design uses the secondary data available in public domain such as the annual reports of the company to source the data.
- For the analysis, quantitative techniques such as prescribed ratios would be used.
- With the help of analysis and pre-existing literature, inferences and conclusions will be drawn from the insights obtained from the analysis.

Analysis & data interpretation

Return on Equity (ROE) serves as a metric to evaluate the efficacy of a company's management in generating income and growth from its equity financing.

Looking at the past five years' data, including the pandemic period, the ROE of HERO MOTORCORP was better until March 21, after which the ROE of TVS is higher than that of HERO. This suggests that the return on equity financing is higher in the case of TVS, and the investors get more returns compared to that of HERO.

This difference, however, was high in March 23, and HERO performed better the latter year to reduce the ROE gap with its competitor to 4%, making it a marginal difference in the returns generated from equity financing.

The gap in the year of Mar-23 can be attributed to the post-pandemic recovery of the company and other factors such as capex which reduce the overall Net Income of the company.

ROE	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
TVS	19%	16%	17%	24%	25%
HERO	25%	19%	15%	17%	21%

Source: Compiled

While ROE gives an understanding as to how the equity capital is being managed to generate returns, we must also take a look at the other sources of financing and hence warrants the use of ROCE, which takes into account both equity and debt, not just the shareholder's-equity like in the case of ROE.

ROCE of HERO had seen a sharp fall of 14% (from 33% in Mar-20 to 19% in Mar-22) while its counterpart TVS had a smaller decline of 2% in the same period. Post-Mar-22, both companies saw an increase in their ROCE.

The ROCE of HERO had gone up by 10% in two years and that of TVS had only seen an increase of 4% in their ROCE.

ROCE	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
TVS	13%	11%	11%	14%	15%
HERO	33%	25%	19%	24%	29%

Source: Compiled

TVS shows more stability in the returns generated during the period of study, while HERO shows more fluctuations and sharp inclines and declines.

The automobile industry is a capital-intensive industry and, in such industries, a study on the operating profit margin should be performed to gain a better understanding of the factors that led to the variances. The OPM gives us the operational efficiency of the company and takes out the components of tax, and interest, which are a result of the company's financing abilities and not the operational aspects of the company. In short, we can directly compare the company's operational efficacies without having a bearing of the company's capital structure and other financing decisions.

OPM	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
TVS	12.01%	11.49%	11.31%	12.59%	14.05%
HERO	13.91%	13.11%	11.02%	12.00%	13.85%

The OPM of both companies declined from Mar-20 to Mar-22 and has seen a consistent increase after that. While initially, Hero had marginally better OPM compared to its counterpart, since Mar-22 TVS had marginally better OPM with a maximum difference of 0.59% and that can be seen reducing to 0.15% in Mar-24. Both companies have reported the OPM to be more than that of the industry average, which is usually between 10%-11%.

Source: Compiled

While the companies adapt to the modern technology and spearhead innovation, it is evident that liabilities and expenses are increasing. This must be in a way that would not compromise the company's liquidity and leverage. To check the same, we can employ the two key ratios, Current and Quick ratios to compare both the companies on the anvils of liquidity and the ability to meet short-term liabilities.

	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
Current Ratio					
TVS	0.971	0.966	0.928	0.885	1.02
HERO	2.02	1.75	1.92	1.57	1.46

The current ratio of HERO had been fluctuating throughout the period while that of TVS had almost remained constant in the past four years.

HERO might appear to be a better option due to its higher liquidity. However, the current ratio is designed to assess how efficiently a company can settle its short-term obligations. This ratio is influenced by key working capital elements like trade receivables, inventory, and trade payables. An increase in finished goods inventory might suggest that product sales are slowing down, while an excess of raw materials could hint at ineffective production planning. Similarly, a surge in trade receivables often means the business is heavily reliant on credit sales and is facing delays in collecting payments. On the other side, elevated trade payables can reflect the company's ability to secure favourable credit terms from its suppliers. Some firms operate by collecting immediate payments from customers while deferring payments to suppliers on credit. This can result in a current ratio below 1—but this is not necessarily problematic. In fact, it indicates a strategic model where customer payments fund operations. A very high current ratio could reflect underutilized working capital, while a significantly low one warrants a deeper dive into the company's financial dynamics.

Despite a surface-level impression that a lower current ratio might be a negative signal, companies with strong leverage over their suppliers and clients can deliberately maintain negative working capital. They often prefer this setup because it enables them to run operations on supplier funds without incurring any an interest—making it a financially sound and strategic move.

Source: Compiled

The quick ratio is more a stringent liquidity ratio as it does not consider the assets, which are current assets, but cannot be converted to cash immediately like that of the inventory. Higher ratio can be better, however, the same cuts down the returns as cash is not a good source for generating returns.

Quick Ratio	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
TVS	0.853	0.841	0.809	0.785	0.914
HERO	1.72	1.47	1.65	1.28	1.21

The trend of quick ratio of the companies is like that of their current ratios. HERO had significant fluctuations and TVS had almost remained constant in the last 4 years.

Source: Compiled

DuPont analysis

Hero MotoCorp:

Financial Ratios	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
DuPont analysis for ROE					
PAT margins/ Net profit margin	12.44%	9.42%	7.84%	8.23%	9.91%
Total Asset Turnover ratio	1.49x	1.34x	1.31x	1.43x	1.44x
Financial leverage	1.37x	1.50x	1.42x	1.44x	1.48x
Return on Equity	25%	19%	15%	17%	21%

Source: Compiled

Between 2020 and 2022, the Return on Equity (ROE) experienced a sharp decline from 25% to 15%. This drop was attributed to a steep 37% fall in net profit margins, decreasing from 12.44% to 7.84%. This suggests that the company faced mounting operational costs or pressure on pricing strategies, directly impacting profitability.

A drop in asset turnover, moving from 1.49x to 1.31x, also contributed to the decline, indicating a decrease in how effectively the company was using its assets to generate revenue.

By 2024, ROE rebounded to 21%, supported by noticeable improvements in core operational metrics. Net profit margins improved from 7.84% to 9.91%. Asset turnover rose from 1.31x to 1.44x. Leverage remained stable between 1.44x and 1.48x.

We must not forget the fact that the industry of automobiles is capital intensive and is deeply affected by COVID 19. The sales during the period have gone down significantly and hence the metrics such as net profits and asset turnover are affected because of the same.

Financial leverage increased steadily from 1.37x to 1.48x during this period. This pattern hints at debt financing for its technology. This method can boost ROE in the short term.

Net profit margin peaked at 12.44% in 2020 but experienced compression over the next two years. This can be attributed to the COVID-19 crisis. While it recovered to 9.91% in 2024, it remains below the 2020 peak. Asset turnover, after declining in 2022, improved steadily and approached near pre-decline levels by 2024, indicating recovery in the sales post COVID.

The rebound in ROE since 2022 has been primarily driven by improved margins and better asset utilization, supported by controlled leverage. However, since margins have not fully recovered to 2020 levels, some challenges in sustaining long-term profitability remain. Investors should continue to monitor whether efficiency gains and prudent leverage can maintain ROE growth without adding undue financial risk.

TVS motor company:

Financial Ratios	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
DuPont analysis for ROE					
PAT margins/ Net profit margin	3.31%	3.06%	3.11%	4.16%	4.31%
Total Asset Turnover ratio	0.98x	0.89x	0.90x	0.91x	0.93x
Financial leverage	5.87x	5.71x	6.12x	6.36x	6.20x
Return on Equity	19%	16%	17%	24%	25%

Source: Compiled

Between 2021 and 2024, the company witnessed a strong resurgence in its return on equity (ROE), rising from 16% to 25%. This significant recovery was primarily fuelled by a 39% boost in net profit margins from 3.06% to 4.31%. At the same time, asset turnover gradually increased from 0.89x to 0.93x, indicating better use of resources to drive revenue. Throughout this period, financial leverage remained notably high, ranging between 5.7x and 6.36x.

The leverage level peaked at 6.36x in 2023. This approach played a major role in shaping ROE outcomes, with leverage contributing 60% to 70% of total ROE each year. For example, in 2024, the ROE of around 25% was a result of the combined effect of 4.31% profit margin, 0.93x turnover, and 6.20x leverage, signifying the compounding impact of financial gearing.

However, the reliance on heavy leverage brings financial risk. High debt levels leave the company more vulnerable to interest rate increases or declines in earnings.

The company's ROE revival since 2021 has been driven by better profitability and deliberate leverage strategies. However, future sustainability will depend on the firm's ability to uphold its margins and gradually improve asset use.

The internal dynamics of a company tend to influence its stock market performance. Therefore, understanding how the market perceives these firms becomes crucial for the research. The Price-to-Earnings (PE) ratio offers a quick insight into how a stock is valued. The PE ratio indicates how much investors are willing to pay for each unit of the company's earnings. For example, a PE of 2 implies that an investor is ready to spend twice the company's EPS to buy a share of the stock.

PE	Mar-20	Mar-21	Mar-22	Mar-23	Mar-24
TVS	22.63	46.77	39.28	38.52	60.62
HERO	8.76	19.95	19.78	16.69	25.21

Source: Compiled

When comparing the PE ratios of TVS and HERO, we observe that both move in a similar pattern, following the industry trends. TVS always holds the higher PE ratio, While HERO's PE ratio lies around the industry average of 24.1.

TVS's stock may be overvalued by industry standards. The consistently elevated PE ratio signals that the stock could be overbought, making it more expensive against its actual earnings performance.

Findings

- Capital structure has a strong bearing on the ROCE and ROE of both companies.
- The Enterprise Value (EV) calculations are affected by equity and debt, providing a direct relationship with the capital structure.
- Hero MotoCorp has more reliable and safe returns and capital structure compared to the TVS Motor Company.

Conclusions

- Hero MotoCorp generates more stable returns as opposed to TVS motor company.
- TVS motor company is over-levered and is highly exposed to interest rate risk.
- TVS Motor Company shares are expensive compared to both industry standards and HERO MotoCorp.

Suggestions

- Analysis of both companies' capital structure and its changes, and their bearing on the financial performance, must be conducted.
- It is to be researched if the same has any bearing on the Enterprise Value calculations using various models.
- Another valuation method such as the P/BV ratio, can be calculated and compared to check the valuation of the stock, not just relying on the P/E ratio.

Recommendations

- A separate study on capital structure and its bearing on ROE, ROCE of the companies.
- It is also to be examined if the Enterprise Value calculation has any relationship with the capital structure of the company.
- The interest rate exposure can be tried and quantified in further research.

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